

Whole-genome sequencing of *Pediococcus pentosaceus* 252371_901 isolated from honey bee gastrointestinal tract

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Abstract

Pediococcus pentosaceus 252371_901 is a lactic acid-producing bacterium (LAB) isolated from *Apis mellifera intermissa* gastrointestinal tract. It has been identified as candidate for probiotics exhibiting β -galactosidase activity and inhibitory effects on both carbohydrate-hydrolases: α -glucosidase and α -amylase. The complete genome sequence assembly of *P. pentosaceus* 252371_901 determined in this work was submitted to the Gen Bank database and assigned accession number GCA_033088855.1.

Introduction

Probiotic microorganisms are generally lactic acid bacteria (LAB), which are dominant members of the gut microbiome in humans and animals where they perform a number of important functions, such as protecting the host from harmful micro-organisms, boosting the host's immune system, improving food digestibility and reducing metabolic disorders (Robles Alonso and Guarner, 2013; Cani, 2018).

LABs are also frequently found in dairy products and fermented food (Ramos *et al.*, 2020; Ağagunduz *et al.*, 2021). They are used during food production, nutritional supplementation, agriculture, and human-animal medicine (Bintsis, 2018). They are good candidates for innovative and promising alternative therapeutics against antibiotic-resistant pathogens and for metabolic engineering (Nataraj *et al.*, 2020; Lim and Shin, 2020; Yadav *et al.*, 2022; Regassa *et al.*, 2021).

We previously isolated LABs from honey bee gastrointestinal tract (Ben-Miled *et al.*, 2023-a) because the identification of new strains from unconventional sources is very important since mechanism of probiotic action may vary from one probiotic to another (Terpou *et al.*, 2019). The isolated strain *Pediococcus pentosaceus* 252371_901 was selected for its potential probiotic properties (Ben-Miled *et al.*, 2023-b) in order to determine its genome sequence. The whole-genome sequencing (WGS) is a promising method to identify key genes involved in these properties.

Material and methods

Pediococcus pentosaceus 252371_901 is a lactic acid-producing bacterium (LAB) isolated from honey bee gastrointestinal tract Ben-Miled *et al.* (2023-a). The isolates were grown in De Man Rogosa Sharpe (MRS) agar supplemented with 2% fructose and 0.1% L-cysteine and incubated under anaerobic conditions at 37 °C for 72 h. The isolates were stored at -80 °C in MRS broth supplemented with glycerol (20%) (Ben-Miled *et al.*, 2023-b).

Genome sequencing methods

The genomic DNA of *P. pentosaceus* 252371_901 was sequenced at Microbes NG using Illumina HiSeq technology. The DNA extraction, the Illumina genome sequencing and assembly were conducted by Microbes NG (The BioHub, Birmingham, UK) according to their protocols <https://microbesng.com/>. The complete genome sequence was annotated using the Prokka at NCBI and taxonomic identification of the genomes sequences was performed by Kraken.

Results

The complete genome sequence assembly of *Pediococcus pentosaceus* 252371_901 has been deposited in the NCBI GenBank (Accession no. GCA_033088855.1). The sequence analysis reveals that the genome comprised 1704559 bp with the average length of coding genes 118.834 bp, with 37.26 % GC content, 55 types of tRNA and one cluster of tmRNA, the whole genome was predicted to contain 1688 protein coding genes (CDSs) (Table 1).

Acknowledgments

The sequencing of the bacterial strains was supported by the GetGenome initiative of The Sainsbury Laboratory, Norwich, UK, with support from the Gatsby Charitable Foundation and the Biotechnology and Biological Sciences Research Council (BBBSRC).

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Table 1: Summary statistics for *Pediococcus pentosaceus* genome

Bacterial species	<i>Pediococcus pentosaceus</i>
Strain	252371_901
Genome size (bp)	1704559
% GC	37.26%
Number of contigs (≥ 1000 bp)	17
Largest contig (bp)	427639
Meancoverage (X)	118.834
Number of reads	429110
N50 (bp)	334367
protein-coding genes	1688
tRNA number	55
tmRNA number	1
SRA accession no.	SRS18479872
Assembly accession no.	GCA_033088855.1